

Interactive Conceptual Design of Structural Equilibrium based on Sparse Ground Structures and ADMM

Jonas WARMUTH^{*a}, Pierluigi D'ACUNTO^b, Corentin FIVET^a

^a Structural Xploration Lab (SXL), Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)
Passage du Cardinal 13b, CH-1700 Fribourg, Switzerland
+41 21 693 85 28

^b Professorship of Structural Design, TUM School of Engineering and Design
Technical University of Munich, Munich, Germany

*Corresponding author: jonas.warmuth@epfl.ch

Abstract

Conventional approaches to designing sound structural forms typically involve either adapting well-known or catalogued types or seeking optimal solutions to well-defined problems. Limited methods are available for generating and exploring structural forms outside of these established practices. This paper presents a computational design framework aimed at early design stages to explore diverse yet efficient discrete structural forms in static equilibrium. The method comprises two main steps: layout optimization and geometry optimization. In the first step, layout optimization based on sparse ground structures is employed to explore structural concepts beyond well-established types. In the second step, geometry optimization, the structural forms obtained from the layout step are refined to meet user-defined design goals and constraints. This is accomplished by minimizing a proximity function following the concept of constraint projections, a method derived from the Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM). This paper presents a new formulation for ensuring static equilibrium through the constraint projection method. Hence, the framework offers advantages in computation speed and flexibility of constraints. With no need for a predefined structure or topology, the framework enables an unbiased exploration of structural forms. This results in an interactive, flexible, and fast exploration of diverse design options in the conceptual design phase. The framework is implemented into a digital tool for the Rhino/Grasshopper environment and applied to a series of application studies to demonstrate its usability for conceptual structural design.

Keywords Computational structural design, Interactive design, Form-finding, Structural exploration, Layout optimization, ADMM

1 Introduction

The early design phase of any project offers the highest possible design freedom and is highly influential for the overall design success [1]. It is therefore crucial to explore a wide range of design options to gain a solid understanding of the design task, while respecting both architectural intentions and structural necessities [2],

33 as stated by the Italian engineer Pier Luigi Nervi [3]: “The methods of bringing [...] loads down to the
34 foundations [...] with the minimum use of materials were interesting, but never enough, I still remember the
35 long and patient work to find an agreement between the static necessities [...] and the desire to obtain
36 something which for me would have a satisfying appearance.”

37 In this article, the early structural design phase is referred to as Conceptual Structural Design (CSD). This
38 phase is understood as the process of conceptualizing a structure based on desired design goals and constraints,
39 ultimately developing a structural concept that delineates its general shape and load-bearing behavior. The
40 overarching goal is therefore – as outlined by Nervi – to achieve a structure that is both aesthetically pleasing
41 and structurally efficient.

42 In this context, the choice of models is key as it influences how load-bearing design ideas are conceptualized,
43 validated, and communicated. Especially within the collaboration of architects and engineers, models can
44 facilitate a shared understanding of design concepts and structural principles [4]. Discrete equilibrium models,
45 such as strut-and-tie bar networks, are particularly effective in this regard. They work by representing force
46 flows and structural behavior without immediate materialization, focusing on the interdependent relationship
47 of form and forces only. In the realm of CSD, discrete equilibrium models are developed for a dominant load
48 case and have proven useful across various materials [5,6]. Closely linked to such models is graphic statics
49 [7,8], formalized in the second half of the 19th century. Graphic statics consists of two interdependent diagrams,
50 the form and force diagram, and has the advantage of making forces visible through the latter, providing a
51 solid foundation for modelling structural concepts in early-stage design. Its intuitive nature makes it an
52 excellent tool for the design of structures, as evidenced by its use in iconic structures like Robert Maillart's
53 Salginatobel Bridge [9,10], the Eiffel Tower [11], or more recently, the Collier Memorial [12].

54 In recent years, efforts have been made to develop computational tools that allow to generate and control
55 discrete equilibrium models in static equilibrium. Hence, assisting architects and engineers during the
56 conceptual phase, and supporting the creation of innovative and sound design concepts. To be effective in
57 these early stages, such tools must possess specific characteristics: they should offer an intuitive understanding,
58 function interactively, and provide real-time feedback on proposed designs. Additionally, they should foster
59 the generation of diverse yet efficient structures while maintaining control over design options [13]. Although
60 several computational tools have been proposed, it remains challenging to incorporate all of the above
61 mentioned features, especially to ensure both structural diversity and efficiency.

62 In previous research [14], a computational method was developed for designing and exploring discrete
63 equilibrium models from the ground up. This method, based on a custom layout optimization, enabled the
64 generation of structural forms beyond specific topologies and typologies. However, it had limitations. Since it
65 relied on layout optimization, the resulting forms were constrained by a pre-defined bar network, or ground
66 structure, leading to indirect geometric control. This made it difficult to apply explicit geometric constraints,
67 refine designs, or create form-active structures.

68

69 This article addresses these limitations and extends previous work by introducing a design method that
70 incorporates a new geometry optimization. The framework consists of two key steps: first, the layout
71 optimization from prior research is used to generate an equilibrated global layout. Second, the newly developed
72 geometry optimization, based on minimizing a proximity function and using constraint projections, allows for
73 direct incorporation of user-defined constraints and the generation of form-active structures. This approach
74 offers more precise geometric control, overcoming the limitations of the original method. Together, layout and
75 geometry optimization provide a robust framework for designing and exploring structural forms with any
76 geometric, static, or combined constraints.

77 The article is structured as follows. Section 2 provides the research context and the original contributions of
78 this article. Section 3 gives an overview of the proposed design method. Section 4 explains the methodology
79 of Step 1, the custom layout optimization. In Section 5, Step 2, the new geometry optimization engine is
80 explained. Section 6 delivers two distinct application studies. Sections 7 and 8 provide a discussion and a
81 conclusion, respectively.

82 **2 Research context**

83 Three kinds of computational tools are identified and reviewed. Computational form-finding tools (Section
84 2.1), performance-driven tools (Section 2.2), and exploration-focused approaches (Section 2.3). Research gaps
85 and contributions are presented in Section 2.4.

86 **2.1 Computational form-finding tools**

87 The largest category of computational tools is based on the concept of form-finding, which can be seen as a
88 special form of geometry optimization that mostly solves nonlinear problems. When designing cable nets,
89 structural membranes, and thin-walled shells – i.e. in the absence of inherent bending capacity – the structure
90 can only bear forces through its shape and form-finding is required. Nevertheless, the benefits of form-finding
91 extend beyond these specific structural types, enabling the design of more efficient structures across various
92 domains. Therefore, form-finding principles can be effectively applied to CSD.

93 Traditionally, form-finding relied on physical models, exemplified by the hanging chain models of Antoni
94 Gaudì [5], the plaster-soaked textile models of Heinz Isler [15], or the soap film models of Frei Otto [16] based
95 on the ideas first introduced in Hooke's law of inversion from 1676 [17].

96 With the advent of the computational age, this paradigm has shifted towards digital methodologies [18]. An
97 important milestone was set by Linkwitz and Schek [19] with the Force Density Method (FDM). A great
98 advantage of the FDM is that it converts a nonlinear form-finding problem to a linear one. This advantage,
99 however, is brought with the cost of flexibility of use as force densities – i.e., force-to-length ratios for all
100 members of the structure – have to be introduced a priori. Efforts to overcome this limitation were made by

101 formulating a nonlinear extension of the FDM [20–22]. This, however, reintroduces a nonlinear problem to be
102 solved. In addition, utilizing force densities as design drivers still presents a challenge due to their abstract
103 nature. Moreover, it is challenging to apply user-specific constraints to the formulation, and an input topology
104 is required beforehand.

105 Addressing the abovementioned issue with force densities and allowing the formulation of additional design
106 constraints, Ohlbrock and Schwartz [23] and, subsequently, Ohlbrock and D’Acunto [24] formalized the
107 Combinatorial Equilibrium Modelling (CEM), a computational framework for the form-finding and conceptual
108 design of structures, rooted in recent developments in graphic statics [25–27]. Later on, the CEM was extended
109 with Automatic Differentiation [28] and combined with Graph Neural Networks [29] to simplify the input
110 handling. However, including additional design constraints requires the computation of first and second-order
111 derivatives, which may cause issues with respect to computational cost and, therefore, might not allow real-
112 time feedback. Similar to the FDM, an input topology is required.

113 Other relevant approaches are so-called direct geometric strategies. These methods assemble equilibrium
114 conditions and additional design constraints in one large system of equations. A well-known example is the
115 Statically-Geometrically Coupling by Kemmler [30,31]. Yet, it demands careful attention during problem
116 setup, as the formulated constraints must avoid contradictions and ambiguity. As this is hard to determine for
117 more complex problems, formulations can be over- or underdefined – i.e., either no solution or infinite
118 solutions exist. Instead of solving one large system of equations, it is also possible to reformulate the form-
119 finding task as an optimization problem, aiming to satisfy a set of constraints, including equilibrium.
120 Describing form-finding as an optimization problem can also be found in [32], where algorithmic
121 differentiation [33] is used to speed up computation. Takahashi and Ney [34] presented an approach based on
122 the concept of constraint projections to form-finding and included constraints. Takahashi [35] later extended
123 it with the implementation of global objectives. Their approach is based on force densities for equilibrium
124 computation, which can pose challenges for applying explicit force constraints. In general, the great advantage
125 of direct geometric strategies is that they are versatile, customizable, and computationally fast. A drawback,
126 however, is that it is not guaranteed to end up at a structure in static equilibrium. In addition, a preliminary
127 geometric configuration of the structure and an initial distribution of internal forces is required. It is also
128 important to mention that these approaches use optimization as a sub-routine to solve a form-finding problem
129 rather than a main driver in the process. This stands in contrast to the group of tools reviewed in the following.

130 **2.2 Performance-driven tools**

131 Another category of computational methodologies employs optimization algorithms to generate conceptual
132 designs. These algorithms typically focus on a primary objective, such as minimizing volume. A pertinent
133 example of this approach is demonstrated in the research conducted by He and Gilbert [36], who used truss
134 layout optimization based on the ground structure approach [37] and combined it with geometry optimization
135 as a post-processing step to rationalize the results. Their findings resulted in the Grasshopper plugin Peregrine

136 [38]. Martinez [39] introduced the ‘growth method’, in which new joints and bars iteratively extend a sparse
137 structure. Similar to that, Jiang et al. [40] presented an alternating linear programming (LP) problem for
138 geometry optimization combined with topological subdivision operations. He et al. [41] have proposed a
139 computationally efficient optimization framework in which a linear programming truss layout optimization is
140 employed to generate close-to-optimal designs. Park et al. [42] discussed the potential use of layout
141 optimization at the conceptual design stage.

142 All these methodologies employ optimization routines as the primary mechanism for generating design
143 candidates. While one objective in CSD is to create efficient structures, a common misconception is
144 prematurely introducing optimization techniques as a main driver in the design process to ensure efficiency.
145 This approach has several drawbacks: (1) optimization techniques often fail to capture the manifold complexity
146 inherent in design tasks, (2) it can lead to overly similar designs that lack diversity, and (3) it perpetuates the
147 erroneous belief that one optimal design can be absolutely achieved [43,44]. Nevertheless, when used
148 appropriately, optimization techniques can still benefit early-stage design.

149 **2.3 Exploration-focused approaches**

150 Several computational strategies have been developed to assist designers at the early stage of design with a
151 focus on exploring and navigating the potential solution space. Often, metaheuristic optimization methods,
152 like genetic algorithms, have been employed to explore structural forms. An early example is ParaGen [45] by
153 von Buelow. This tool operates on structures with a predefined topology. The evolutionary exploration
154 mechanism controls nodal coordinates and imposes the nodes’ relocation until specific design criteria are met.
155 Mueller and Ochsendorf [46] contributed to the development of performance-informed design, which resulted
156 in the creation of StructureFit. This approach employs genetic algorithms to enable designers to investigate
157 and enhance design candidates by selecting parents for crossover and mutation. The topology of the design
158 candidates is determined by the designer's input, with the examples presented in a 2D format. Saldana Ochoa
159 et al. [47] combined the CEM with machine learning algorithms to explore and navigate the design space.
160 Harding and Shepherd [48] worked on meta-parametric design, resulting in Biomorpher [49], a plugin for
161 Grasshopper that employs interactive genetic algorithms to explore and optimize any parametric definition
162 created by the designer. Mirtsopoulos and Fivet [50,51] presented a generative approach based on grammar
163 rules and combined it with the interactive genetic algorithms in Biomorpher. A major advantage of employing
164 meta-heuristic optimization algorithms is their ability to handle diverse problems due to their independence
165 from differentiable (in-)equations. Nonetheless, a significant challenge associated with their use is that the
166 underlying formulations may lead to computationally expensive procedures.

167 **2.4 Research gaps and contributions**

168 Although computational methods and tools for generating structural design concepts are available, most focus
169 either on performance and do not allow for an in-depth exploration of the design space, or they support

170 exploration without allowing to include user-specific design constraints. Moreover, some tools are limited to
 171 a certain domain, i.e., only 2D structures or only compression/tension-only structures.

172 Among form-finding tools, some rely on force densities, which could make it challenging to control the design
 173 due to their abstract nature. Moreover, when constraints are included, this usually leads to an optimization
 174 problem where first- and second-order derivatives must be computed. This, however, may affect computational
 175 efficiency and, therefore, does not allow for a smooth design process in which instant feedback is required,
 176 and one can go back and forth easily in the design generation [46]. Another limitation of these methods is their
 177 reliance on predefined input forms or topologies. This requirement necessitates that users possess a preliminary
 178 concept of their intended design, thereby hindering an unbiased and comprehensive exploration of potential
 179 solutions.

180 To address these limitations, this paper extends previous work [14] and introduces an interactive computational
 181 design framework for generating discrete equilibrium models. The framework combines structural (topology
 182 and geometry) exploration with performance-informed design by combining layout optimization from
 183 previous research [14] with a new geometry optimization method. Key features are the ability to incorporate
 184 any static or geometric constraint without the need for derivative calculations and the absence of a need for
 185 predefined input forms or topologies, hence facilitating an unbiased exploration of structural forms.
 186 Additionally, the theoretical framework is implemented into a computational tool, providing an interactive
 187 approach with real-time feedback. The framework's applicability is demonstrated through realistic design
 188 scenarios.

189 3 Design framework overview

190

191

Table 1. Notation and symbols.

Notation		
Variable	Unit	Description
\mathbf{x}	[-]	vector of variables
\mathbf{s}	[kN]	vector of internal bar forces
V	[m ³]	volume
\mathbf{l}	[m]	vector of bar lengths
\mathbf{a}	[m ²]	vector of cross-section areas
σ_T/σ_C	[MPa]	stress limits in tension/compression
\mathbf{B}	[-]	equilibrium matrix
\mathbf{p}	[kN]	vector of external forces
L	[m]	length/span
Q	[kN]	point load
m	[-]	number of bars
n	[-]	number of nodes
ρ_L/ρ_U	[m]	lower/upper bound for bar lengths
φ_L/φ_U	[kN]	lower/upper bound for internal bar forces
v	[-]	number of constraints

θ	[var.]	proximity function
d	[var.]	distance of variable to its projection
$P(\mathbf{x})$	[var.]	projection(s) of variables \mathbf{x}
\mathbf{n}	[m]	node with its coordinates x,y,z
\mathbf{R}	[kN]	residual force vector
Symbols		
		bar in tension
		bar in compression
		external force
		support
		node

192

193 Figure 1 gives an overview of the framework, which consists of five main steps. During the initialization
 194 (Figure 1a) users can place support, load, and regular nodes that serve as the basis for a structure in equilibrium,
 195 which is calculated in the subsequent steps. Based on the placed nodes, a ground structure is created (Figure
 196 1b), i.e. all the placed nodes are connected with each other, forming a complete graph. These connections later
 197 become bars that belong to a structure. In this step, users can also define which bar lengths are allowed and
 198 what maximum bar forces can occur, which already allows the process to be guided in a preferred direction.

199 The generated ground structure serves as the starting point for a layout optimization in the next step (Figure
 200 1c), where an optimal subset of bars is determined as the one that minimizes static action – i.e. an early
 201 approximation of bar volume – while maintaining equilibrium at the nodes, adhering to the defined bar lengths
 202 and forces. Although optimization significantly streamlines the outcome, users have a substantial influence on
 203 the result since nodes are placed individually. As such, exploring various structural forms that are yet efficient
 204 is ensured. The variables for this step are solely the bar internal forces $\mathbf{x} = [\mathbf{s}]$, leading to a linear programming
 205 problem to be solved. Nodes do not move during this layout optimization.

206 Next, a subsequent geometry optimization is performed. This step is meant to refine the structure obtained
 207 from the layout optimization to meet user-specific design goals. For that, the obtained structure from the layout
 208 step is taken as a starting point for the geometry optimization (Figure 1e). If required, the structure can also be
 209 altered manually before proceeding with the geometry optimization. To initiate this process, constraints are
 210 formulated. These can be of any kind: geometric, static or a combination of both. For example, in Figure 1e
 211 four constraints are formulated: the cyan bars are required to have equal lengths, the orange bars are required
 212 to be vertical, and the yellow nodes are required to move to a specified position. In addition, equilibrium at
 213 each node is required. After formulating the constraints, a geometry optimization is performed to deliver a
 214 structure in equilibrium that meets the intended constraints (Figure 1f). In contrast to the layout step, variables
 215 are now nodal coordinates $\mathbf{x}_{\text{nodes}} = [\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}]$ and the bar internal forces $\mathbf{x}_{\text{forces}} = [\mathbf{s}]$, summarized in a variable
 216 vector $\mathbf{x} = [\mathbf{x}_{\text{nodes}}, \mathbf{x}_{\text{forces}}]$. This shifts the formulation from a LP problem to a nonlinear programming (NLP)
 217 problem to be solved, in this paper by using constraint projections. The outcome structure (Figure 1g) can then
 218 again be modified by going back to step (a) until users are satisfied with the result. This iterative nature of the

219 workflow is installed to support an open-ended design process. In addition, the geometry optimization can also
220 be used as a standalone form-finding step. In this case, users need to provide an initial structure with which to
221 work. Sections 4 and 5 are now explaining the layout step and the geometry step in detail.

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Figure 1. Workflow of the proposed design framework.

224 4 Structural exploration through custom layout optimization

225 Within the domain of numerical layout optimization, the most common method is the ground structure
 226 approach [37], its extensions [36,52], and variations [39]. The great advantage of layout optimization is its
 227 ability to deliver highly efficient structures, which is a critical factor in design processes where resource
 228 conservation is important. However, a drawback of it – and optimization procedures in general – is its tendency
 229 to generate similar designs that lack diversity, making it less desirable for early-stage design. This challenge
 230 is the focus of the subsequent discourse and was part of previous work [14]. Section 4.1 outlines the
 231 conventional ground structure approach's functionality, paving the way for Section 4.2, which introduces a
 232 customized approach that harnesses the benefits of conventional layout optimization, i.e. computing efficient
 233 structures, while introducing design flexibility and user control, making it well-aligned for early-stage design
 234 efforts, where exploration and rapid feedback are crucial.

235 4.1 Conventional ground structure approach

236 The principal idea of the conventional ground structure approach is to interconnect a set of predefined nodes
 237 by bars that build the ground structure (Figure 2b). Subsequently, the basic plastic formulation of the ground
 238 structure approach solves a continuous LP problem by identifying the set of bars that minimizes volume while
 239 respecting static equilibrium and stress constraints (Figure 2c). This yields to the following optimization
 240 problem:

$$\min_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{s}} V = \mathbf{I}^T \mathbf{a} \quad (1a)$$

subject to

$$\mathbf{B} \mathbf{s} = \mathbf{p} \quad (1b)$$

$$\sigma_T \mathbf{a} - \mathbf{s} \geq 0 \quad (1c)$$

$$\sigma_C \mathbf{a} + \mathbf{s} \geq 0 \quad (1d)$$

$$\mathbf{a} \geq 0 \quad (1e)$$

241 where V is the volume of all members, \mathbf{I} is a vector of all bar lengths, and \mathbf{a} is a vector of all bar cross-section
 242 areas. \mathbf{B} is an equilibrium matrix containing the direction cosines of all bars. \mathbf{s} is the vector of bar internal
 243 forces, and \mathbf{p} is the vector of external nodal loads. σ_T and σ_C are stress limits in tension and compression.

244

245 *Figure 2. Conventional layout optimization with (a) load and support conditions specified, (b) nodes interconnected by*
 246 *bars, building the 'ground structure'; (c) optimal layout generated by solving the underlying LP problem; (d) final*
 247 *structure in equilibrium*

248 The advantage of this procedure is that, as a linear programming problem, it can be solved relatively quickly.
 249 For small-sized problems, such as the one in Figure 2, solutions are achieved on a standard computer in real-
 250 time, i.e., $\Delta t \leq 0.001$ sec. Moreover, it delivers the most efficient structure possible according to the preset
 251 boundary conditions. However, when problem size increases, the ground structure becomes denser and
 252 computational cost may be an issue. Another drawback concerning the exploration of different forms is that
 253 even though the resolution of the ground structure can be altered, the resulting structures belong to the same
 254 typological family with slight improvements in performance, as shown in Figure 3. This raises the question of
 255 how to mitigate this rigidity in the results and achieve a broader variety of outcomes.

257 *Figure 3. Conventional layout optimization, where higher resolution in the ground structure improves performance but*
 258 *yields the same type.*

259 4.2 Customized design approach

260 Unlike the conventional ground structure approach, which utilizes a predefined grid of nodes, the customized
 261 design methodology proposed by Warmuth et al. [14] permits users to place nodes in desired locations (Figure
 262 4a) strategically. These user-defined nodes are subsequently employed to construct a sparse ground structure
 263 for further layout optimization (Figure 4b). Thus, the optimized structure is significantly influenced by the
 264 nodes placed by the designer while still yielding the best possible performance according to the preset
 265 boundary conditions and chosen nodes (Figure 4c+d). Besides placing nodes, designers can also specify
 266 intervals for bar lengths and bar internal forces to guide the process in a preferred direction. This method
 267 empowers designers to impose their preferences and specify the locations for nodes and bars. However, there
 268 is no guarantee that every node will be retained in the final solution. Additionally, the pre-placed nodes can be
 269 modified or removed at any point during the process, allowing designers to observe the effects on the final
 270 structure in real-time. This allows direct interaction with the design brief. Alternatively, the nodal positions
 271 could also be defined randomly in an automated way, which leads to the direct generation of a large set of
 272 diverse design outputs.

273

274

Figure 4. Workflow of the customized ground structure approach.

275

In general, the objective function of a classical layout optimization is to minimize the volume of a structure. However, in early-stage design, usually, no material has yet been decided upon and, therefore, no stress limits can be stated, as formulated in (Equation 1c+d). This means that no volume can be computed, as, according to (Equation 1a), volume is defined as the multiplication of bar lengths with their cross-section areas, while the cross-section area of a bar i is defined as

279

$$a_i = \frac{s_i}{\sigma} \quad (2)$$

280

Assuming a constant stress limit in tension and compression, i.e. $\sigma_T = \sigma_C = \sigma$, the relation of a bar internal force s_i and its cross section area a_i is constant, too. By choosing a value for this constant, e.g., $\sigma = 1$, then

281

$$a_i = |s_i| \quad (3)$$

282

(Equation 1a) can therefore be rewritten as

$$\min_{\mathbf{s}} V = \mathbf{1}^T |\mathbf{s}| \quad (4)$$

283

The multiplication of bar internal force magnitudes and corresponding bar lengths was already introduced by Sergio Musmeci in his book *La Statica e le Strutture* [53,54], where he called this value *total static action* Φ . There, the computation of Φ is defined as the sum of the products of bar lengths with their force magnitudes, separating bars in tension (T) from bars in compression (C):

284

285

286

$$\Phi = \sum_T s_T l_T + \sum_C |s_C| l_C \quad (5)$$

287 Therefore, under the assumption of constant material strength and maximum utilization rate in each bar,
 288 minimizing *total static action* can be seen as a substitute for minimizing volume, which leads to the following
 289 reformulated optimization problem to be solved:

$$\min_{\mathbf{s}} \Phi = \mathbf{I}^T |\mathbf{s}| \quad (6a)$$

subject to

$$\mathbf{B}\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{p} \quad (6b)$$

290 The rewritten optimization problem is a LP problem, too. The advantage of using a LP formulation is that it is
 291 computationally efficient, an important feature for any interactive tool at the conceptual design stage. Design
 292 goals, as shown in Figure 4, are not described yet in this formulation. Therefore, the current formulation needs
 293 to be extended. One way to extend the previous formulation is to introduce additional constraints. For this,
 294 upper and lower bounds for bar lengths and force magnitudes are introduced.

$$\rho_L \leq l_i \leq \rho_U \quad (6c)$$

$$\varphi_L \leq s_i \leq \varphi_U \quad (6d)$$

295 ρ_L , ρ_U and φ_L , φ_U are lower and upper bounds for bar lengths and internal bar forces, respectively. In previous
 296 research [14], the formulation was further extended to allow for more user control, but this changed the
 297 problem formulation to a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problem, leading to increased
 298 computational complexity. To retain real-time computation, this framework only uses the constraints described
 299 in (Equation 6c+d).

300
 301 *Figure 5. Structures resulting from the application of the customized groundstructure approach for different node*
 302 *locations. Note the greater typological diversity compared to the results of Figure 3. Φ is the resulting static action*
 303 *normalized for a unit load Q and a unit length L .*

304 The advantage of this step is that structural concepts can be explored easily and in real time. Figure 5 presents
 305 six designs, with the top-left design resulting from classical layout optimization, showing a total static action

306 of $\Phi = 2.43\text{QL}$. The other five designs also perform well, with total static actions of $\Phi = 2.43\text{QL}$ (+ 0%),
 307 2.50QL (+ 3%), 2.62QL (+ 8%), and 2.78QL (+ 14%) with one design being even better performing with $\Phi =$
 308 2.40QL (- 1%). Yet, these designs are very different in their form and topology, unlike results of Figure 3
 309 generated with the conventional ground structure approach. Generating such a set of diverse structures would
 310 not have been possible with the conventional approach.

312 *Figure 6. Modifying a chosen structural type.*

313 Moreover, a generated structural form can be modified, too, by keeping the global structural idea, but exploring
 314 slight changes in form and topology. Figure 6 shows on the left-hand side one selected structure from Figure
 315 5 next to three nodal variations with performance ranging from 2.59QL to 2.86QL. The fundamental load-
 316 bearing behaviour, in which a cable spans over multiple compression struts, is maintained, but the topology
 317 and form change. This provides insight into the load-bearing properties of the chosen form and aids in the
 318 decision-making process for a suitable structure. This approach parallels a sensitivity study concerning the
 319 form.

320 A limitation of this approach, however, is that user-specific constraints can hardly be applied and that the
 321 generation of form-active structures is mostly infeasible. Both limitations are addressed in the geometry step
 322 of the design framework, which is explained in the following section.

323 5 Geometry optimization based on ADMM

324 5.1 Conventional geometry optimization

325 The problem formulation of (Equation 1) is now considered while allowing the geometry to be changed – i.e.
 326 the connectivity of the structure is fixed, and the position of the nodes can be altered. This allows to formulate
 327 constraints that refer to the nodal coordinates $\mathbf{x}_{\text{nodes}} = [\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}]$ and bar internal forces $\mathbf{x}_{\text{forces}} = [\mathbf{s}]$ – e.g.
 328 certain target lengths or forces for bars, or constraints for nodes to be on predefined curves or surfaces.
 329 Accordingly, this also leads to a change of variables. As a reminder, in the layout optimization, the variables
 330 were $\mathbf{x} = [\mathbf{s}]$, whereas now they are $\mathbf{x} = [\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{s}]$, leading to the optimization problem from (Equation 6):

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{s}} \Phi = \mathbf{l}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z})^T |\mathbf{s}| \quad (7a)$$

subject to

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z})\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{p} \quad (7b)$$

331 Alternatively, its generalization refers to a constrained optimization problem of the form:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}} f(\mathbf{x}) \quad (8a)$$

subject to

$$\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (8b)$$

332 where $f(\mathbf{x})$ is the objective function, e.g. the total static action Φ of a structure, \mathbf{x} the set of variables, and $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})$
 333 a set of equality constraints – e.g. equilibrium constraints of the form
 334 $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z})\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{p}$. A common way to solve such a constrained optimization problem is to convert it to an
 335 unconstrained one by formulating the augmented Lagrangian [55]:

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}) = f(\mathbf{x}) + \boldsymbol{\lambda}^T \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) + \frac{\mu}{2} \|\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})\|^2 \quad (9)$$

336 where $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ is a vector of Lagrange-multipliers and μ is a penalty parameter with $\mu \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$. This can be solved
 337 using, e.g. the Newton-Raphson method, which requires the derivatives $\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\lambda})$

$$\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}) = \nabla f(\mathbf{x}) + \boldsymbol{\lambda}^T \nabla \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) + \mu \nabla \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (10)$$

338 and $\nabla_{\mathbf{xx}}^2 \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\lambda})$

$$\nabla_{\mathbf{xx}}^2 \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}) = \nabla^2 f(\mathbf{x}) + \sum_{i=1}^v \lambda_i \nabla^2 g_i(\mathbf{x}) + \mu \nabla \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) \nabla \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})^T + \mu \sum_{i=1}^v g_i(\mathbf{x}) \nabla^2 g_i(\mathbf{x}) \quad (11)$$

339 where v is the total number of equality constraints. Due to the typical non-linearity, and potential non-
 340 smoothness and non-convexity of $f(\mathbf{x})$ and $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})$, solving such problems can be challenging [55].

341 5.2 Geometry optimization using constraint projections

342 To avoid this, inspiration is drawn from Bouaziz et al. [56,57] and their Local-Global optimization method for
 343 projective dynamics and for shaping discrete geometry using constraint projections, which they originally
 344 derived from Combettes [58], a technique in signal processing for constraint satisfaction of problems that may
 345 not have feasible solutions. The key idea of the method is to replace the solving of constraint equations $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) =$
 346 $\mathbf{0}$ by the minimization of a shape proximity function $\Theta(\mathbf{x})$ that computes the weighted sum of squared distances
 347 of a set of variables to their projection onto a collection of v constraints $\{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_v\}$. In its original
 348 formulation, the variables \mathbf{x} of the shape proximity function $\Theta(\mathbf{x})$ encountered only nodal coordinates $\mathbf{x} =$
 349 $[\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}]$. In this article however, bar internal forces \mathbf{s} are variables, too, leading to $\mathbf{x} = [\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{s}]$. Therefore,
 350 the term "shape proximity function" is no longer appropriate, as it now incorporates considerations beyond

351 mere shape, specifically static aspects. Thus, the term *proximity function* will be used throughout the remainder
352 of this article. Let $d_j(\mathbf{x})$ measure the ‘least amount of change’ in \mathbf{x} to satisfy a constraint g_j . The proximity
353 function is

$$\Theta(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_j^v w_j d_j(\mathbf{x})^2 \quad (12)$$

354 where v denotes the number of constraints and w_j are non-negative weights that control the relative importance
355 of each constraint g_j . $d_j(\mathbf{x})^2$ describes the squared distance of a set of variables \mathbf{x} to its projection $P_j(\mathbf{x})$ onto a
356 constraint g_j . Thus, the proximity function can be rewritten as

$$\Theta(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_j^v w_j \|\mathbf{x} - P_j(\mathbf{x})\|_2^2 \quad (13)$$

357 This function determines how well all constraints are satisfied. Finding a solution that minimizes the proximity
358 function to $\Theta(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ therefore satisfies all constraints. Otherwise, a least squares solution is found. In order
359 to solve this, the optimization is divided into a local and global step, executed in an alternating update scheme.

- 360 1. Local step: Compute the projection $P_j(\mathbf{x})$ for each constraint g_j using the current \mathbf{x} .
- 361 2. Global step: Compute a new \mathbf{x} based on the projection $P_j(\mathbf{x})$ of all constraints $\{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_v\}$.

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Figure 7. Two iterations of the local-global optimization scheme with $w_j = 1$. The local step computes the projections $P_j(\mathbf{x})$ using the current estimate \mathbf{x} . The global step updates \mathbf{x} by minimizing $\theta(\mathbf{x})$, keeping the projections $P_j(\mathbf{x})$ fixed. At each step, $\theta(\mathbf{x})$, illustrated by the sum of the error bars, will decrease, even if some of the individual elements increase, adapted from [56].

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369

According to Bouaziz et al. [56], this scheme converges monotonically to a local minimum. The convergence rate depends on the conditions of the problem and the projection functions involved. Figure 7 shows the two step process for three constraints $g_1(\mathbf{x})$, $g_2(\mathbf{x})$, $g_3(\mathbf{x})$ and two iterations k and $k+1$.

370

5.3 Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers

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Overby et al. [59] pointed out that the local-global optimization scheme used in [57] is essentially a special form of the Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers [60] (ADMM) where no objective function is provided, and only constraints must be satisfied. ADMM is a method for solving an optimization problem of the form

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{z}^*} f(\mathbf{x}^*) + h(\mathbf{z}^*) \quad (14a)$$

subject to

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}^* - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{z}^* = \mathbf{0} \quad (14b)$$

375 The constraints can be incorporated into the objective function by formulating the augmented Lagrangian

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{z}^*, \boldsymbol{\lambda}) = f(\mathbf{x}^*) + h(\mathbf{z}^*) + \mu \boldsymbol{\lambda}^T (\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}^* - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{z}^*) + \frac{\mu}{2} \|\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}^* - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{z}^*\|^2 \quad (15)$$

376 The ADMM algorithm computes an optimal point of \mathbf{x}^* , \mathbf{z}^* and $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ following the iteration scheme:

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1}^* = \underset{\mathbf{x}^*}{\operatorname{argmin}} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{z}_k^*, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_k) \quad (16a)$$

$$\mathbf{z}_{k+1}^* = \underset{\mathbf{z}^*}{\operatorname{argmin}} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_{k+1}^*, \mathbf{z}^*, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_k) \quad (16b)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\lambda}_{k+1} = \boldsymbol{\lambda}_k + \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_{k+1}^* - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{z}_{k+1}^* \quad (16c)$$

377 In the local-global solver presented earlier in this paper, no objective function is provided. Consequently, the
 378 ADMM iteration scheme in (Equation 16a-c) simplifies to alternating updates of \mathbf{x}^* (16a) and \mathbf{z}^* (16b) only.
 379 In the context of the local-global optimization scheme, the \mathbf{x}^* -update in ADMM corresponds to the global step,
 380 where a new \mathbf{x} is computed as the weighted average distance to the projections $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x})$. The \mathbf{z}^* -update in ADMM
 381 corresponds to the local step, where the projections $\mathbf{P}_j(\mathbf{x})$ are computed independently. A similar procedure is
 382 used in the Grasshopper plugin Kangaroo2 [61] as well as for the form-finding method utilizing force-densities
 383 by Takahashi and Ney [34]. An important difference between the approach in [34] and this work is that explicit
 384 force values are used here. This offers the significant advantage of (1) the ability to formulate direct force
 385 constraints and (2) the provision of an intuitive understanding of chosen forces.

386 A drawback of the local-global solver, however, is the absence of an objective function and the inability to
 387 formulate hard constraints. Takahashi [35] addressed this issue by extending the local-global solver, following
 388 the ADMM methodology, and introducing an objective function. However, this extension is beyond the scope
 389 of this article, which employs the local-global solver as described in (Equation 13).

390 5.4 Computation of equilibrium

391 A structure will be in static equilibrium if all its nodes are in static equilibrium. Following the logic of the
 392 alternating optimization scheme presented in Section 5.2, an equilibrium constraint is formulated for each node
 393 of a structure and is solved individually and independently of other nodes. For example, a structure with five
 394 nodes needs five equilibrium constraints. In the local step, equilibrium is computed at each of the five nodes.
 395 Figure 8 shows how equilibrium at the local node level is computed. The node in question is herein called \mathbf{n}_0 .
 396 The variables at the local node level are the coordinates of \mathbf{n}_0 , here $\mathbf{x}_{\text{nodes}} = [n_{0x}, n_{0y}, n_{0z}]^T$, and the
 397 magnitudes of the internal bar forces of all bars connected to \mathbf{n}_0 , here called $\mathbf{x}_{\text{forces}} = [s_1, s_2, s_3]^T$. All

398 variables are summarized in a vector $\mathbf{x} = [n_{0x}, n_{0y}, n_{0z}, s_1, s_2, s_3]^T$. Within the scope of local node
 399 equilibrium, the connected nodes $\mathbf{n}_1, \mathbf{n}_2, \mathbf{n}_3$ do not move and serve as virtual supports.

400

401 *Figure 8. Computation of static equilibrium at one node during the local step, showing the form diagram \mathbf{F} and the*
 402 *force diagram \mathbf{F}^* in the initial configuration and the projected configuration where the node is in static equilibrium;*
 403 *blue vectors in \mathbf{F}^* in compression, red vectors in tension, and green vectors for external forces.*

404 Equilibrium at a node is achieved when the residual force vector \mathbf{R} , as shown in the force diagram \mathbf{F}^* in Figure
 405 8, is null. The residual force vector can be computed as the sum of all bar internal force vectors and the external
 406 force vector.

$$\mathbf{R} = \left(\sum_i^h \mathbf{s}_i \right) + \mathbf{p} \quad (17)$$

407 where $\mathbf{p} = [p_x, p_y, p_z]^T$ represents the external force vector, h the number of connected bars and \mathbf{s}_i the i^{th}
 408 internal force vector. \mathbf{s}_i can be computed as

$$\mathbf{s}_i = s_i \cdot \mathbf{d}_i \quad (18)$$

409 where s_i is the bar internal force magnitude and \mathbf{d}_i is the normalized direction vector of a connected bar, which
 410 can be computed as

$$\mathbf{d}_i = \frac{\mathbf{n}_i - \mathbf{n}_0}{\|\mathbf{n}_i - \mathbf{n}_0\|} \quad (19)$$

411 For \mathbf{n}_0 to be in static equilibrium:

$$\mathbf{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{0} \quad (20)$$

412 must be fulfilled. In three dimensional space \mathbf{R} consist of three parts:

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} R_x \\ R_y \\ R_z \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

413 where R_x is the residual force in x-direction and can be written as

$$R_x = \frac{s_1(n_{1,x} - n_{0,x})}{l_1} + \frac{s_2(n_{2,x} - n_{0,x})}{l_2} + \frac{s_3(n_{1,x} - n_{0,x})}{l_3} + p_x \quad (22)$$

414 or generalized as

$$R_x = \left(\sum_1^h \frac{s_i \Delta x_i}{l_i} \right) + p_x \quad (23)$$

415 where h is the number of connected bars, $\Delta x_i = n_{i,x} - n_{0,x}$, $l_i = \sqrt{\Delta x_i^2 + \Delta y_i^2 + \Delta z_i^2}$, and p_x is the x-

416 component of a given external load. R_y and R_z are computed similarly in y- and z-directions. By solving the

417 optimization problem

$$\min_{x,y,z,s} \mathbf{R} \rightarrow 0 \quad (24)$$

418 an equilibrium configuration can be computed. One direct way to solve this optimization problem is to use the

419 Newton-Raphson method in which one iteration is written as

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{R} \nabla \mathbf{R}^\dagger \quad (25)$$

420 where $\nabla \mathbf{R}^\dagger$ is the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse of $\nabla \mathbf{R}$. Since $\nabla \mathbf{R}$ is not squared, a real inverse $\nabla \mathbf{R}^{-1}$ cannot

421 be computed. This results from the fact that for the local equilibrium calculation, 3 equilibrium conditions

422 concern $3+h$ variables, where h presents the number of bars connected to the node. Consequently, the

423 equilibrium calculation at node level is generally underdetermined. Solving the optimization problem

424 described above, therefore, yields the equilibrium state that is closest to the initial state, which corresponds to

425 the smallest change in \mathbf{x} . (Equation 25) can be efficiently solved since

$$\nabla \mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{i=1}^h \frac{-s_i(\Delta y_i^2 + \Delta z_i^2)}{l_i^3} & \sum_{i=1}^h \frac{s_i \Delta x_i \Delta y_i}{l_i^3} & \sum_{i=1}^h \frac{s_i \Delta x_i \Delta z_i}{l_i^3} & \frac{\Delta x_1}{l_1} & \frac{\Delta x_h}{l_h} \\ \sum_{i=1}^h \frac{s_i \Delta y_i \Delta x_i}{l_i^3} & \sum_{i=1}^h \frac{-s_i(\Delta x_i^2 + \Delta z_i^2)}{l_i^3} & \sum_{i=1}^h \frac{s_i \Delta y_i \Delta z_i}{l_i^3} & \frac{\Delta y_1}{l_1} & \dots & \frac{\Delta y_h}{l_h} \\ \sum_{i=1}^h \frac{s_i \Delta z_i \Delta x_i}{l_i^3} & \sum_{i=1}^h \frac{s_i \Delta z_i \Delta y_i}{l_i^3} & \sum_{i=1}^h \frac{-s_i(\Delta x_i^2 + \Delta y_i^2)}{l_i^3} & \frac{\Delta z_1}{l_1} & & \frac{\Delta z_h}{l_h} \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

426 is available analytically. $\nabla \mathbf{R}$ consists of three rows for the residual force vector in x-, y-, and z-directions. The

427 number of columns, however, is not fixed as it depends on the number of bars connected to a node. Columns

428 1-3 refer to the coordinate variables x, y, and z; columns four and higher refer to the force variables. For

429 instance, if two nodes are connected to \mathbf{n}_0 , there are two columns for force variables, i.e., five columns in total.

430 After solving, the new variables $\mathbf{x}^* = [n_{0,x}^*, n_{0,y}^*, n_{0,z}^*, s_1^*, s_2^*, s_3^*]^T$ are the projection $P_j(\mathbf{x})$ for the equilibrium
 431 constraint g_j at node \mathbf{n}_0 . By computing the projections for all other nodes, the local step of the alternating
 432 update scheme is fully computed, considering static equilibrium.

433 Besides static equilibrium, other constraints are available. The following constraints are implemented in the
 434 current framework. However, any constraint can be incorporated if a projection $P_j(\mathbf{x})$ can be computed.

435 *Table 2. List of geometric and static constraints available in the framework.*

Constraint type	Geometric	Static
	- Target length	- Equilibrium
	- Equal length	- Target force
	- Points on plane	- Equal force
	- Points on surface	
	- Points on curve	
	- Colinear points	

436 A broader selection of constraints can be found in Takahashi and Ney [34], Bouaziz et al. [56], or Piker [61].

437 6 Application studies

438 In this section, two application studies are conducted to demonstrate the potential of the proposed design
 439 framework. In the first study, three design options for a single span bridge are developed. In the second study,
 440 pure form-finding for a curved bridge is performed, following only the method described in Section 5.

441 6.1 Simple bridges with combined approach

442 6.1.1 Design task

443 The following conceptual designs are generated using the combined approach explained in Sections 3, 4, and
 444 5. The goal of this study is to generate a conceptual design for a single-span bridge. Three different design
 445 options are explored. Figure 9 illustrates the general setting for this design scenario. The intended bridge spans
 446 a length of 25.0 m and has a width of 5.0 m, as indicated by the light grey deck area. Beneath the deck flows
 447 a river, with a clearance of 4.0 m from the deck to the water level. While it is permissible to have structural
 448 elements below the deck, it is preferable to minimize their presence to allow boats to pass underneath the
 449 bridge unobstructed. All designs are generated for a dominant load case of vertical loads, simulating self-
 450 weight, dead load, and live loads. The loads are discretized, with each load being $Q = 1.0$ kN. This does not
 451 represent a realistic load but serves for clarity and simplicity. Since the results calculated using the method
 452 above are linearly scalable, the load applied makes no technical difference. Additionally, the calculated values
 453 for total static action do not possess absolute significance. What is important, however, is their relative
 454 significance when comparing different variants created under the same conditions. By default, eight individual
 455 loads are applied, although this number can be adjusted as needed. It is crucial that the total force remains
 456 constant and the distribution remains uniform to maintain comparability across various designs. Supports for

457 the structure can be positioned anywhere except within the river itself, delineated by the grey area in Figure 9,
458 which includes the shores on either side of the river, the embankments, and the deck surfaces. No additional
459 constraints are imposed regarding the height of the bridge.

460

461

Figure 9. Initial set up for design task.

462 6.1.2 Generated designs

463 Option 01

464 For the first bridge option, development begins on one side, with the other side added symmetrically at a later
465 stage. Consequently, only four loads are applied instead of the usual eight.

466 In the initial step, depicted in Figure 10a, the layout step is conducted. Four loads are evenly spaced, and
467 supports are positioned at the midpoint of the embankments. Nodes are then placed in between, forming an
468 initial structural concept represented by red and blue lines. There are more nodes placed than nodes utilized in
469 the final structure, as indicated by the nodes connected with grey lines. The algorithm omits these surplus
470 nodes as they are unnecessary for computing an efficient structure in static equilibrium based on the provided
471 ground structure. Figure 10a thus presents the overarching conceptual idea of the design: an arch-like
472 configuration extending from the loads to the supports, reinforced by tension cables above.

473 This initial structure is now subject to refinement, marking the second step in the presented framework, known
474 as the geometry step (see Figure 1). In this phase, specific constraints are formulated, and topological
475 modifications are introduced, as illustrated in Figure 10b. The fundamental load-bearing concept remains
476 unchanged, but the resolution is adjusted. Specifically, the number of compression bars connecting the tension
477 cables to the compression bars at deck level increases from two to six. This adjustment also raises the number
478 of cables from three to seven. To maintain uniformity, two length constraints are imposed: 1) all compression
479 bars are required to have equal lengths (cyan lines), and 2) all cables connecting these bars must also have
480 equal lengths (orange lines). Additionally, a constraint is applied to the location of supports, ensuring they are
481 positioned on the surface of the embankment (highlighted by the yellow node and arrow).

482 After formulating these constraints, the computation starts and delivers the result shown in Figure 10c, where
483 the structure in equilibrium is displayed, meeting all defined constraints. Subsequently, the structure can be
484 mirrored symmetrically on the other side of the deck, finalizing the conceptual design for option 01. Figure
485 10c also depicts bar internal forces as well as the total static action of $\Phi = 468.6$ kNm. The computation time

486 on an Intel i9-11900H @ 2.50GHz CPU is $\Delta t = 0.001$ sec. for the layout step and $\Delta t = 3.62$ sec. for the
 487 geometry step. Design options 2 and 3 follow the same procedure. Importantly, these steps can be iterated or
 488 adjusted to refine the design concept further or explore alternatives, facilitated by efficient computation times
 489 and immediate feedback on node placements and constraints. Following this procedure, a potentially broad
 490 range of diverse options can be explored.

491

492 *Figure 10. Steps for designing bridge option 1: (a) generation of global design concept by placing nodes for the layout*
 493 *step, delivering a structure in static equilibrium with the internal forces shown on a bar chart, ordered from left to*
 494 *right, (b) input structure for the geometry step that is inspired from the layout step in (a), in addition, design-specific*
 495 *constraints are applied, (c) result of the geometry step with a structure in static equilibrium that meets the formulated*
 496 *constraints, with the internal forces shown on the bar chart, ordered from left to right.*

497 **Option 02**

498 For option 2, two supports are positioned at the midpoint of each respective end edge of the deck. Nodes are
 499 symmetrically placed above and below the deck, with one node positioned between every two loads. This
 500 configuration results in the equilibrium structure shown in Figure 11a. It is evident that in this symmetrical
 501 arrangement, the compression and tension components are mirrored precisely on the deck surface. This
 502 structure serves as the initial framework for subsequent refinements.

503 As illustrated in Figure 11b, the resolution of the bars connected to the loads is increased during the refinement
 504 process. This adjustment aims to achieve a more uniform distribution of loads. The spacing between the loads
 505 should remain equal, as indicated by the constraint represented by orange lines. Additionally, two bars, rather
 506 than one, extend to each support. These bars are supposed to obtain equal forces to ensure uniform utilization
 507 of the bars. In addition, the two supports on each side should be positioned at the corners of the deck.
 508 Figure 11c displays the final equilibrium structure. The mirrored distribution of compression and tension
 509 components remains unchanged but with a finer resolution as intended. Computational times of $\Delta t = 0.009$
 510 sec. and $\Delta t = 0.62$ sec. are recorded for the layout and geometry steps, respectively.

511

512 *Figure 11. Steps for designing bridge option 2: (a) generation of global design concept by placing nodes for the layout*
 513 *step, delivering a structure in static equilibrium with the internal forces shown on a bar chart, ordered from left to*
 514 *right, (b) input structure for the geometry step that is inspired from the layout step in (a), in addition design-specific*
 515 *constraints are applied, (c) result of the geometry step with a structure in static equilibrium that meets the formulated*
 516 *constraints, with the internal forces shown on the bar chart, ordered from left to right.*

517 **Option 03**

518 For design option 3, the supports are positioned more centrally, exploring the feasibility of placing supports
519 alongside the shores rather than solely on the surfaces at deck level and the embankments, as seen in previous
520 examples. This shift also entails a redistribution of the eight individual loads, which are now positioned on
521 either side of the supports. Furthermore, nodes are strategically placed above the deck to align precisely in one
522 plane with the load nodes and the supports, ensuring a cohesive and uniform appearance. Figure 12a illustrates
523 the resulting equilibrium structure, which essentially comprises two identical individual structures.

524 Since the supports would currently be suspended in mid-air, adjustments are necessary, leading to the second
525 step: the geometry step. In this phase, the topology is adjusted so that three compression struts, instead of one,
526 connect the supports to the tension components. These compression struts are designed to carry equal forces
527 to ensure balanced loading, as indicated by the cyan-colored lines. Additionally, the distance from the supports
528 to the deck and from the highest point to the deck must be equal (red lines). It is crucial to maintain the
529 condition that all nodes lie in one plane (pink surfaces), which was initially the case but needs to be explicitly
530 enforced due to potential changes in bridge height. Finally, a constraint specifies that the supports must align
531 with the river level to prevent them from being suspended in mid-air (yellow nodes and arrows).

532

533 *Figure 12. Steps for designing bridge option 3: (a) generation of global design concept by placing nodes for the layout*
 534 *step, delivering a structure in static equilibrium with the internal forces shown on a bar chart, ordered from left to*
 535 *right, (b) input structure for the geometry step that is inspired from the layout step in (a), in addition design-specific*
 536 *constraints are applied, (c) result of the geometry step with a structure in static equilibrium that meets the formulated*
 537 *constraints, with the internal forces shown on the bar chart, ordered from left to right.*

538 Figure 12c shows the final structure with all constraints successfully fulfilled. The computation times are $\Delta t =$
 539 0.006 sec. for the layout step and $\Delta t = 0.55 \text{ sec.}$ for the geometry step, both of which fall within the real-time
 540 calculation range. Furthermore, the force distribution diagram in Figure 12c illustrates twelve compression
 541 bars of equal length, confirming adherence to the requirement for equal forces across the connecting
 542 compression bars.

543 When comparing the three different options, it can be observed that their total static action ranges from 137.0
 544 kNm to 468.6 kNm with design 03 being the most efficient one with a static action of 137.0 kNm. It should be
 545 noted that this comparison should be approached with caution, as the number and distribution of loads are not
 546 identical, even though their total resultant is consistent. Nonetheless, this comparison offers a preliminary
 547 assessment of the structural performance and can serve as valuable decision support in the early stages of

548 design. Since the computation time of the three options ranges from 0.001 sec to 0.009 sec for the layout step
549 and from 0.55 sec. to 3.62 sec. for the geometry step, a significant amount of design options could be observed,
550 always ensuring real-time feedback and user interactivity.

551 **6.2 Form-finding of a curved bridge**

552 **6.2.1 Boundary conditions**

553 The objective of this example is to determine the equilibrium form of a curved bridge, utilizing solely the
554 geometry optimization method delineated in Section 5. As explained in Section 5, the geometry step can
555 function autonomously as a form-finding procedure to compute an equilibrium configuration based on a
556 specified input topology. Thus, the input topology is not required to be in equilibrium initially. Figure 13
557 illustrates the boundary conditions for this design scenario. The primary objective is to connect two dead-end
558 segments of a hiking trail that terminate at a cliff, thereby creating a continuous trail and providing hikers with
559 the opportunity to enjoy a scenic view from an elevated position on the bridge. The design includes two fixed
560 supports at the termini of the hiking trails, which remain stationary throughout the form-finding process and
561 the exploration of various design alternatives. Additional supports, if required, can be introduced both below
562 and above the deck level. Consistent with previous examples, the loading conditions are represented by
563 discretized loads of $Q = 1.0$ kN that simulate dead load, self-weight, and live load for the assumed form-giving
564 load case. Moreover, the bridge deck must maintain a horizontal position to ensure a comfortable passage.

565

566 *Figure 13. Boundary conditions for bridge case study.*

567 The dimensions of the bridge are specified as 30.0 m between the supports located at the ends of the hiking
568 trails. The maximum distance from the imaginary line connecting these supports to the farthest point on the
569 bridge is 10.0 m. This point is fixed and immovable, serving as a reference for the path layout of the bridge
570 deck.

571 **6.2.2 Exploration and form-finding**

572 Figure 14a-f presents six design options that are in static equilibrium. For each option, from left to right, the
573 figures include the initial configuration with applied constraints, the form-found structure in static equilibrium,

574 the bar internal forces, the total static action, and the computation time required to reach convergence. The
575 total static action of the designs ranges from 290.0 kNm to 1701.1 kNm, and the computation time from $\Delta t =$
576 0.85 sec. to $\Delta t = 7.92$ sec. The longer computation time for option (c) compared to the other structures may
577 be caused by the initial choices of node locations and internal bar forces for this option. When these initial
578 values are farther from the final equilibrium state, the solver requires more iterations to converge. These
579 structural concepts provide an initial insight into the design task, illustrating potential structural configurations.
580 The key information conveyed includes the relative efficiency of different structures in carrying loads,
581 highlighting which designs are more or less effective. This preliminary assessment assists in the decision-
582 making process by identifying a preferred design direction for further investigation. This step aims to offer an
583 understanding of the bridge's behaviour for various forms and to ensure that no excessively resource-intensive
584 structure is selected. The data produced serves as decision support for designers, acknowledging that certain
585 aspects of design cannot be quantified. In a practical scenario, multiple designs might be selected for further
586 development. However, for the sake of clarity, only one design is further investigated in this example.

587 The selection is made for option (a) due to its relative efficiency, evidenced by a total static action of 699.6
588 kNm. Additionally, the flow of forces is clearly defined, contributing to a clean and expressive appearance. In
589 this design, loads from the deck are transferred via the stayed cables to the two suspension cables, and
590 subsequently to the supports. The horizontal components of the stayed cables are counterbalanced by a
591 compression ring in the deck, ensuring structural integrity in three-dimensional space. Despite the vertical
592 orientation of the mast, which is limited to carrying vertical loads, the structure remains stable due to its spatial
593 configuration, mitigating any concerns of potential tipping.

594

595
596

Figure 14. Exploration of design options for a curved bridge, (left) input structures with applied constraints, (center) structures in static equilibrium after form-finding, (right) bar chart of internal bar forces, ordered from left to right.

597 **6.2.3 Refinement**

598 The selected design will now be further investigated, with particular emphasis on analyzing variations in the
 599 position of the mast's apex because the length and orientation of the mast significantly determine the visual
 600 appearance of the bridge. Therefore, a sensitivity analysis will be carried out to assess the impact of altering
 601 the mast's inclination from its current vertical orientation on both structural efficiency and visual appearance.
 602 A fundamental design constraint demands that the structure maintains symmetry, thereby restricting the
 603 movement of the mast exclusively to the y-z plane.

604 Figure 15a depicts a side view of the bridge, illustrating the apex of the mast and its associated degrees of
 605 freedom. In this analysis, the top node is permitted to move up to 3.0 m horizontally in both left and right
 606 directions along the y-axis. Vertically, the top node can move up to 7.0 m above its initial position and 3.0 m
 607 below its initial position along the z-axis.

608

609 *Figure 15. Refinement of a selected design, (a) side view of the selected design with the top node to be moved vertically*
 610 *and horizontally, (b) plot of resulting static actions within the defined move interval, (c) six different configurations for*
 611 *mast node placement.*

612

613 Figure 15b plots the solution space encompassing all feasible mast configurations within the defined interval.
614 Figure 15c-h present selected configurations from this solution space. A minimal static action of 663.3 kNm
615 is achieved with a vertical mast positioned 4.0 m higher along the z-axis, as depicted in Figure 15d. Notably,
616 the solution space can be divided into two distinct regions: one characterized by a relatively flat range of static
617 actions from a local minimum of 663.3 kNm up to 850.0 kNm (green colors), and another region where static
618 action increases rapidly beyond 850.0 kNm, exceeding 1,200.0 kNm (orange colors). This delineation
619 significantly influences the decision-making process regarding mast configuration selection, advocating for
620 designs within the flatter region to avoid inefficiency. Given the flat nature of this region of the solution space,
621 numerous mast configurations can be considered without compromising structural efficiency. In this instance,
622 the initial mast configuration yielding a total static action of 699.6 kNm, depicted in Figure 15g, is kept.
623 Despite maintaining the original mast position, the sensitivity study reinforced this decision and provided
624 valuable insights.

625 **6.2.4 Final design**

626 The current bridge design positions both the cables and the loads at the same location, assuming the loads act
627 as concentrated forces at the midpoint of the deck. However, attaching the cables at this central point would
628 hinder pedestrian movement across the bridge. Therefore, a more practical approach involves attaching the
629 cables to the inner side of the deck. This adjustment introduces an eccentricity e between the cables and the
630 loads, generating a torquing moment

$$M = Qe \quad (27)$$

631 that attempts to rotate the deck clockwise, as depicted in Figure 16a, top. To counteract this torquing moment
632 and maintain structural equilibrium, a horizontal force pair with a distance b between the forces is introduced:

$$M = F_c b = F_t b = Qe \quad (28)$$

633 The compression ring of the bridge can handle the blue force of the horizontal force pair, which was initially
634 present. To manage the horizontal red force, an additional tension ring is necessary (Figure 16a, bottom). This
635 arrangement restores equilibrium to the entire structure. However, the incorporation of an additional tension

636 ring necessitates a refined base structure to accommodate the altered conditions, which leads to a new form-
637 finding process. The finalized design, including the new tension ring, is depicted in Figure 16b.

638

639 *Figure 16. Refinement of the chosen design to account for eccentric loading.*

640 Figure 17 shows a schematic view of the developed design concept to get an impression of how a potential
641 bridge could look like. The bridge is equipped with a glass deck, making the supporting components of
642 tension and compression ring visible. This allows the entire load-bearing process of the bridge to be
643 understood, giving the structure an additional level of transparency. Furthermore, the bridge is sparsely
644 equipped with secondary components to draw attention to its important features.

645

646

Figure 17. Schematic view of the bridge concept.

647 7 Discussion

648 Several key observations were made while working with the introduced framework. In general, computation
649 time is fast, i.e. a few milliseconds for the layout step and up to a few seconds for the geometry step. This
650 allows an interactive and real-time approach when designing and exploring structures. However, measuring
651 the computation time, especially for the geometry step, is only somewhat meaningful, as it highly depends on
652 the chosen initial configuration. An initial geometry that is already close to the final solution and initial forces
653 that are also close to the final equilibrium state are calculated significantly faster than a poorly chosen initial
654 configuration. In the case of the combined approach, an initial configuration that is close to the final solution
655 is already available from the layout step, which partially mitigates this problem and which sets this approach
656 apart from existing ones.

657 A second key feature of the approach is that constraints can be straightforwardly included to guide the design.
658 During the layout step, only length and force magnitude constraints of bars can be applied, whereas, in the
659 geometry step, any geometric or static constraint can be incorporated. Even when constraints are contradictory,
660 the method still finds a least-squares solution, though non-contradictory constraints ensure faster convergence
661 and solution feasibility. Moreover, the two steps – layout optimization and geometry optimization – can be
662 used independently, each with distinct advantages. The layout step does not require a predefined structure or
663 topology, making it valuable at the beginning of a design task for exploring different solutions without bias
664 towards known types or topologies. The geometry step allows for high customization, enabling the definition
665 of any constraints and facilitating the discovery of form-active, or in other words kinematically-unstable,
666 structures such as arches and cable nets or any bending-free spatial arrangement of bars, which is hardly
667 possible in the layout step due to fixed node positions.

668 The framework's simplicity enhances its usability, making it particularly useful in educational settings.
669 Students could generate discrete equilibrium models without extensive prior knowledge, aiding their intuitive
670 understanding of the relationship between form and forces, benefiting both engineering and architecture
671 students.

672 Furthermore, the generated equilibrium models are applicable to different scales, e.g. in the form-finding
673 example in Section 6.2. Globally, an overall form in static equilibrium is generated. Once a design option is
674 selected, it can be further refined, for instance, by modifying the mast position to understand structural
675 behaviour in various configurations. On a finer scale, the method can address design challenges, such as the
676 eccentricity introduced by edge-placed cables on a bridge deck, ultimately leading to the implementation of a
677 tension ring in the structure. While further analysis and modification of the design brief could be pursued, such
678 as allowing the mast to move in more than just the y- and z-directions, this would increase problem size,
679 leading to higher dimensional formulations, making visualization challenging or even impractical. Techniques
680 for dimensionality reduction could be employed to address this issue, but these methods fall outside the scope
681 of this article.

682 Despite its advantages, the framework has certain limitations. In the layout step, only two constraints (lengths
683 and force magnitudes of bars) can be applied, which may limit design flexibility. Other constraints, such as a
684 limitation on the number of bars or nodes, can be applied but would transfer the problem formulation from an
685 LP to a MILP formulation, which would affect computational speed significantly. Since a fast exploration of
686 different options is the main goal in this setting, computational speed is favored more constraints to select
687 from. Additionally, retaining control in the layout step becomes challenging when too many nodes are
688 involved, potentially leading to results that are technically correct but not meaningful in a structural context.
689 The geometry step's effectiveness highly depends on the input values. Performing pure form-finding,
690 therefore, requires a solid structural understanding and a clear vision of the goals. Furthermore, the method
691 sometimes experiences slow convergence, a phenomenon known to be associated with the Newton-Raphson
692 method.

693 Future work aims to address and enhance several aspects of the framework. Improving the computational
694 procedure to boost convergence rate and speed is a priority. This can be achieved by developing an acceleration
695 technique to enhance convergence efficiency further. Introducing the option to include custom constraints will
696 provide greater flexibility in design. Additionally, implementing and comparing other methodologies for
697 geometry optimization could offer new insights and improvements. Incorporating an objective function will
698 provide better control and guidance during the design process. Finally, the method will soon be made available
699 as a plugin for the Rhino/Grasshopper environment, enabling broader access and allowing more users to benefit
700 from the advancements described in this paper.

701 **8 Conclusion**

702 This article presented a computational design framework for discrete equilibrium models aimed at early design
703 stages and the exploration of diverse yet efficient structural forms in static equilibrium. The framework
704 comprises two main steps: a layout and a geometry optimization. In the layout step, custom, sparse ground
705 structures are employed to explore structural concepts beyond well-established types or topologies. In the
706 geometry step, structures obtained from the layout step are refined to meet user-defined design goals. This is
707 performed by minimizing a proximity function following the concept of constraint projections, a method
708 derived from the Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers. Overall, this results in a design framework with
709 rapid computation times, i.e. mere milliseconds for the layout step and a few seconds for the geometry step on
710 a common laptop, ensuring user interactivity and facilitating flexible and swift navigation through diverse
711 design options, including form-active ones. It is important to note that while optimization routines play a
712 crucial role in both steps, they serve as sub-routines within the design process rather than primary design
713 drivers. Likewise, the framework does not require a predefined structure or topology; these are automatically
714 generated within the framework, building on incremental user inputs. At minimum, users must specify (an
715 approximation of) the intended node placements for the structure. The upcoming release of a plugin for the
716 Rhino/Grasshopper environment will democratize access, allowing a wider audience to leverage the benefits

717 of these developments. Overall, the method represents a step forward in the interactive design and analysis of
718 structural forms at early design stages, fostering a deeper understanding of the interplay between form and
719 forces.

720 **Author's contributions**

721 Jonas Warmuth developed the theoretical formalism in the paper with advice from Pierluigi D'Acunto and
722 Corentin Fivet. Jonas Warmuth devised the mathematical interpretations, generation methodologies and their
723 computational implementation. Jonas Warmuth wrote the manuscript in consultation with Pierluigi D'Acunto
724 and Corentin Fivet. All authors provided critical feedback along the development of the research, and
725 supervised the writing of the paper.

726 **Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process**

727 During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used GPT-4o to improve sentence structure. After using this
728 tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the
729 content of the publication.

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731 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could
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